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**A STUDY ON AWARENESS ABOUT GREEN BANKING AMONG HOME MAKERS –
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PALAYAMKOTTAI REGION**

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays business organizations have started following “go green” concept. Banks play a major role in the economic development of the nations. Besides that, banks are also introducing the best practices of green banking in order to protect the environment and to. Green banking means promoting environment friendly practices for sustainable growth and reduces the carbon footprint from the banking industry. This study is conducted to analyze the awareness level among homemakers about green banking in palayamkottai. This study is particularly conducted among the homemakers because they are the real decision makers in a family and they should be well aware of the latest changes in the banking sector. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 80 respondents and 78 were collected back and 3 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 75. Simple random sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents. The result of our study shows that the homemakers are aware of only few green banking products and the government and Banks should create awareness and educate them about the importance of green banking products by providing proper training.

KEY WORDS: Green banking, Homemakers awareness, Problems , Perception

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays business organizations have started following “go green” concept, because there is a change in the attitude of the society towards the environment and they started taking care of the environment. Banks play a major role in the economic development of the nations. Besides that, banks are also introducing the best practices of green banking in order to protect the environment and to. Green banking means promoting environment friendly practices for sustainable growth and reduces the carbon footprint from the banking industry. This study is conducted to analyze the awareness level among homemakers about green banking in palayamkottai. This study is particularly conducted among the homemakers because they are the real decision makers in a family and they should be well aware of the latest changes in the banking sector.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. G. Prakash Raj (2017) explain in his study that green banking is the corporate social responsibility of every banks. Along with the focus on the green banking initiatives the bank should also take care of their lending policy and it encourages the customer’s business transaction in an environmental friendly manner.

Satheesh Kumar.C (2017) explain in his study that banks should take necessary action to educate the general public about green banking and its products.

Dr.S.R. Easwari (2019), states that the government should play major role and formulate green policy guidelines and financial incentive for going green. Proper training and educational programs by banks for green initiatives will actually make green banking successful.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the concept of green banking.
- To check the awareness of green banking among homemakers.
- To create the awareness about green banking among general public.
- To identify the problems in following the green banking.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study aims at measuring the level of awareness and the perception of the homemakers towards green baking services. It also focuses to identify the problems faced by them in following green banking services. The result of this study also serves as a basis for additional research in the field of Green banking.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Every research has to face its limitations. Some are controllable and some are not controllable. The limitations of the study are as follows.

- The area of the study is restricted to Palayamkottai only
- This study covers only the homemakers.
- The sample size is restricted to 75.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is a descriptive survey based study. It is mainly based on primary data and secondary data. The primary data is collected by developing a well structured questionnaire mainly taking into consideration the objectives of the study. The questionnaire is circulated among 80 respondents and 78 were collected back and 3 were found incomplete. So the sample size is restricted to 75. Simple random sampling method was adopted for selecting the respondents. The secondary data is collected through books, manuals and websites.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method and chi square techniques are used in this study

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Up to 30 years	40	53
	30 to 40 years	15	20
	40 to 50 years	11	15

	Above 50 years	09	12
Educational qualification	10 th	08	11
	12 th	10	13
	UG	43	57
	PG	14	19
Monthly family income	Less than 15000	30	40
	Rs 15000 – Rs 30000	35	47
	More than Rs 30000	10	13
Types of bank	Public bank	50	67
	Private bank	19	25
	Foreign bank	06	08
Information about green banking services	Bank officials	44	59
	Advertisements	07	09
	TV & Radio	10	13
	Friends&Family members	14	19
Perception towards Green banking services	Vital	08	11
	Essential	43	57
	Desirable	10	13
	Cannot say exactly	14	19

Source: Data collected through questionnaire
The above table

explains that

- Majority (53%) of our respondents belong to less than 30 years of age.
- Majority (57%) of our respondents have completed their UG.
- Majority (47%) of our respondents have a monthly income of Rs 15000 to Rs 30000.
- Majority (67%) of our respondents have their accounts in public sector banks.
- Majority (59%) of the respondents say that they know about green banking services by their bank officials.
- Majority (57%) of the respondents feel that green banking services are essential.

Table 4: Awareness among homemakers about Green banking products

Green banking products	Aware		Not aware	
	No of respondents	% of respondents	No of respondents	% of respondents
Paying bill online	52	69%	23	31%
Online fund transfer	50	67%	25	33%
Green cards	44	59%	31	41%
Green car loan	23	31%	52	69%
Green mortgages	20	27%	55	73%
Green home equity loans	14	19%	61	81%
Green certificates of deposits	08	11%	67	89%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table interprets that majority of the respondents are aware of online bill payment, online fund transfer, green cards and majority of our respondents are not aware of green car loan, green mortgages, green home equity loans and green certificate of deposits.

Table 3: Methods of creating awareness among homemakers about Green banking

Weighted average method is used to analyze the methods of creating awareness among homemakers about green banking

Statement	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Total score	Avg Score	Rank
Make them cheaper by reducing charges/ fees	41	12	9	8	3	299	59.8	I
Incentives to green bank user	10	39	22	3	1	279	55.8	II
Intensive advertisement	23	10	15	20	7	247	49.4	IV
Contacting every customer personally	23	21	18	12	1	278	55.6	III
Giving them the guarantee of data security	15	18	10	16	16	225	45	V

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table it is inferred that majority of our respondents feel that the awareness should be created by reducing the bank charges, providing incentives to green bank user and by contacting every customer personally.

Table 4: Problems faced by homemakers in following green banking system

Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the problems faced by the homemakers in following green banking system

FACTORS	SCORE	AVG. SCORE	RANK
Lack of education	3869	51,59	V
Lack of confidence in handling automatic transaction	3719	49,59	VI

Lack of knowledge of technology	4097	54,63	IV
No direct interaction with the banker	4259	56,79	III
Lack of security and privacy	4682	62,42	I
Technical issues	4511	60.15	II

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

From the above table it is understood that majority of our respondents feel that major barriers in following green banking is lack of security and privacy followed by technical issues and no direct interaction with the banker.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₀1: There is no association between age and the level of satisfaction.

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	34.13	21.03	12	Rejected

Since the calculated value (85.44) is more than the table value (15.507) the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is association between the age of the respondents and their level of satisfaction.

H₀2: There is no association between the age and their perception towards green banking services.

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	4.02	16.919	9	Accepted

Since the calculated value (4.09) is less than the table value (16.919) therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between the age of the respondents and their perception towards green banking services.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- Homemakers are aware of only few green banking products, so the banks should take necessary steps to create awareness among them by constructing a website to provide necessary awareness about green banking products.
- Impart education about green banking among schools and college students.
- There are many problems in following green banking so the government and Reserve Bank of India should shape up concrete guidelines for green banking.
- A separate section should be formed by banks to help the homemakers to carry out their green banking transaction successfully.
- Banks must simplify the methods of usage of mobile banking and internet banking.
- Seminars and workshops should be organized and public meetings must be organized by banks to create awareness among the customers.

Nowadays there is an increase in awareness about the protection and conservation of the environment. But India is in a start up stage regarding the green banking when compared to other countries. Majority of our respondents feel that the green banking initiatives are very essential in this changing environment. But most of the people are not well educated and prepared with the modern automated system so it is the responsibility of banks to educate their customers about their green banking initiatives.

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